

State of the art report on citizen science and sustainable urban transformation frameworks intersection

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CS	Citizen science
CSS	Citizen social science
OS	Open science
OPUSH	Open Urban Sustainability Hubs
SDG	Sustainable development goal
UN	United Nations

Summary

OPUSH is an applied research project that analyzes the role of local knowledge infrastructures for sustainable urban development and finds measures to strengthen these infrastructures. Citizen science experimentation in all involved cities guarantees capacity building and training by means of hands-on activities, where digital and non-digital tools and learning/training material are implemented as well as lessons learned for long-term development of open knowledge hubs.

To correctly envision the experimentation within this project, it is necessary to deeply analyze the two sustainable urban development and citizen science frameworks. After a short description of the frameworks, the document presents a systematic literature review seeking to understand the intersections of these two frameworks.

The literature review evidences that the number of the papers at these intersections is fast growing, while they can be divided into three clusters using the VOSviewer bibliometric mapping software. The analysis of these three clusters, associated to different thematic scopes, allows to evidence the most actual trends and the strongest associations within the terms present in the titles and the abstracts. A qualitative analysis of the most relevant papers for OPUSH allows to tentatively propose a “CS pedestrian pathway to urban sustainable transformation” and to map the issues, collectives, transformation processes as well as methodologies and tools of the intersections of the two frameworks.

This analysis situates the OPUSH project in a rapidly changing environment, where the challenge and value of OPUSH can thus consist of proposing a conceptual frame and of validating it through different case studies.

I. Introduction

I.1. OPUSH summary

OPUSH is an applied research project that analyzes the role of local knowledge infrastructures for sustainable urban development and finds measures to strengthen these infrastructures in an international and transdisciplinary project partnership over a period of three years. In four cities and metropolitan regions, cooperation between universities, libraries, museums, city administration, and civil society are established, and approaches of citizen social science (CSS) are tested in these local networks.

All key activities are focused on the study, development and implementation of inclusive knowledge ecosystems, addressing the gap between sustainability theory and sustainability transformation in practice (in particular the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), The New Urban Agenda and the World Climate Goals COP15). The project pursues a multi-layered approach to applied research and capacity building. By focusing on libraries as knowledge infrastructure and integrating local capacity building networks, capacities are developed on an institutional level to open the collaborative generation of knowledge in society. Citizen science (CS) experimentation in all involved cities guarantees capacity building and training by means of hands-on activities, where digital and non-digital tools and learning/training material are implemented as well as lessons learned for long-term development of open knowledge hubs.

To achieve the project goals, OPUSH builds upon an innovative experimentation and strategic implementation of CS and the related open science (OS) scope in urban sustainability transformation.

This deliverable is framed within WP2, dedicated to establishing communication between partners and create a common approach, which will be carefully connected to the local context of each involved city. Specifically, this document relates to the work done within T2.2 *CS and sustainable urban transformation foundations*. This task is focused on a systematic literature review and analysis on interactions and synergies between CS and urban sustainable transformation frameworks. The goal of this literature review is to gather the necessary knowledge to plan new and relevant research processes at these intersections, also based on the work done in T2.1 *OS and urban transformation landscape analysis in all involved cities*.

In relation to the other work packages of OPUSH, the findings of the systematic literature review are relevant in different ways. For the preparation and implementation of the CS experiments in the partner cities (WP 3), the analysis gives indications on relevant emerging research topics and on already existing knowledge concerning the applied approaches and tools as well as the collected experiences and gained insights. The identified reference literature can also help to refine the overall evaluation framework for the CS experiments (WP 4). In addition, the contents of the texts may also provide knowledge on appropriate approaches to capacity building and dissemination (WP 5).

I.2. Examination of the underlying frameworks

A preliminary and necessary step before the literature review is to carefully examine the “citizen science” and “sustainable urban transformation” frameworks, as a prerequisite to be later able to examine their possible intersection.

I.2.1 Citizen science

The term citizen science (CS) was first used during the mid 90s and has been subject since then to numerous debates around its definition. Almost 30 years after its creation, there is however a broad consensus around a general definition as to the one given in the recently published book “The Science of Citizen Science”:

“Citizen Science broadly refers to the active engagement of the general public in scientific research tasks. Citizen science is a growing practice in which scientists and citizens collaborate to produce new knowledge for science and society” (Vohland et al., 2021).

In this definition, CS is envisioned as a research model that implies the active engagement of the citizens. The definition also makes clear that scientific research and knowledge production are key elements of CS.

While OPUSH is considering CS as a global framing of its research activities, it also focuses on the potential of citizen social science (CSS) as an appropriate and promising perspective. CSS is defined as a “*participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern*” by the CoAct project¹. Other authors also pointed out that citizen social science is “*not only a consolidated set of social science methodologies placed in and out-of-the-lab context, but also social issues or concerns raised by groups of citizens and the ways in which these produce*

¹ See the webpage <https://coactproject.eu/> for more detailed information.

new scientific knowledge. Situating these social concerns at the centre of research, and its public, has important implications in terms of the legitimacy of the research and of giving voice to under-represented or vulnerable groups” (Albert et al., 2021).

While CS was initially rooted into the natural sciences, it increasingly becomes a transdisciplinary methodology, which is incorporating elements of social sciences and humanities and natural sciences in an organic way. Almost all scientific disciplines are now applying CS methodologies to answer to new questions, ranging from fundamental physics, to medicine, linguistics or history, to cite a few.

I.2.2 Sustainable urban transformation

As already discussed in Deliverable 2.1, within the contemporary Urban Studies perspective, the empirical examination of urban transformation is shaped by a theoretical understanding that conceives the urban as a relational space (Davoudi, 2015; Healey, 2006). Urban planning, as a genuine way to achieve urban transformation, is a particularly potential fertile ground, where citizens’ participation within this relational space could be enhanced in many ways. Urban planning is understood as a social activity that follows a rational orientation and is systematically directed towards solving societal problems. This definition of planning includes all forms of planning practice as well as various forms of governance.

Urban transformation is linked to sustainable development since decades. As described in Deliverable 2.1: *Sustainable development, as an international normative concept, has gained momentum in 1987 with the publication of Our Common Future, the Brundtland report of the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development. Sustainable development is defined by this report as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN, 1987).* The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are increasingly defined by specific goals and indicators that also address the urban dimension in many ways and specifically with SDG 11 “Sustainable cities and communities” (UN, 2015). In this respect, sustainability as a political framework does not originate at the urban level but has made a career at the international level since the 1980s, starting with environmental protection agendas, and has gradually been transferred to national and sub-national levels.

In essence, sustainability describes a state, sustainable development a process, and the adjective sustainable a quality or characteristic. Sustainability as a claim for a transformative social and environmental policy requires a time- and place-specific reference, as well as a consideration of different socio-political interests, demands, fields of work and topics. In this sense, neither structures and processes nor the results

of urban planning are sustainable all at once but require a systematic examination and reference.

Sustainable development is not a process without contradictions, but rather involves strategically dealing with conflicts of goals and interests and empowerment. OPUSH seeks to strengthen integrated approaches to urban transformation and sustainable development that include recursive learning and transdisciplinary knowledge integration.

II. Systematic literature review

II.1. Research question

The research question that was collectively formulated by the OPUSH consortium as a driving force for the systematic literature review is the following:

What are the conceptual intersections and synergies between “citizen science” and “sustainable urban transformation”?

With this research question, the aim is to visualize which are both the consolidated and emerging trends situated at the intersection of these two frameworks. The goal is also to determine which synergies, in terms of topics, practices and actors, can serve as a win-win strategy to increase the relevance of the two frameworks.

II.2 Methodology and results

II.2.1 Systematic literature search

As commented in section I.2, CS is now a consolidated methodological framework with a relevant impact in scientific publications (1,443 publications as “citizen science” as a topic in 2021. Source: Web of Science, accessed on the 9th of September 2022²). For this reason, “citizen science” was used directly as a keyword. Meanwhile, “sustainable urban transformation” is addressed in the literature either as a normative, analytical or methodological framework. But the exact topic “sustainable urban transformation” only appears in 58 papers for all years (Source: Web of Science,

² Search for “citizen science” as a topic in all databases supported by Web of Science. Accessed on the 9th of September 2022.

accessed on the 9th of September 2022³). OPUSH is concerned with the methodological potential of citizen science in the context of “sustainable urban transformation”, which is why sustainable development as a normative component and urban transformation as an application practice are of interest. For this reason, a set of keywords were explored, as listed in Table 1 and we included the different components of “sustainable urban transformation(s)”: the urban component (e.g., urban or city or cities), in combination with sustainable (or sustainability) and transformation (or development or urban planning).

citizen science (1)	sustainable urban transformation (2)
“citizen science”	“sustainable urban transformation*” / “urban sustainability transformation*” “urban” / “city” / “cities” “sustainable” / “sustainability” “transformation*” / “development” “urban planning”

Table 1: Keywords collaboratively selected for the literature search.

The systematic literature search was conducted using two different databases to minimize publication bias:

1. Web of Science provided by Clarivate⁴
2. Scopus provided by Elsevier

Even if there is an overlap in coverage because both sources focus on peer-reviewed journals, Scopus indexes more European journals and conferences than Web of Science, with mainly English-language publications and highly ranked journals (Impact Factor). Searching both Web of Science and Scopus, we wanted to guarantee that relevant studies published in other journals and languages are identified and included in our analysis. Avoiding language bias was also one of the reasons for our extensive hand search.

The literature searches in these two different sources are displayed in Table 2. The number of papers is similar in all cases for both databases. Hereafter, the number of papers refer to Web of Science.

The published papers related to CS already occupy a consolidated (8,002 papers in total) and growing (1279 papers in 2020 vs. 1443 papers in 2021) niche within the scientific production (Search #1). Meanwhile, the papers related to sustainable urban

³ Search for “sustainable urban transformation” as a topic in all databases supported by Web of Science. Accessed on the 9th of September 2022.

⁴ We searched the following databases via Web of Science: Web of Science Core Collection; BIOSIS Citation Index; BIOSIS Previews; Current Contents Connect; Derwent Innovations Index; KCI-Korean Journal Database; MEDLINE; SciELO Citation Index; Zoological Record. We used all editions: Science Citation Index Expanded 1900-present, Social Sciences Citation Index 1900-present.

transformation (or transformations) (search #2) or urban sustainability transformation (or transformations) (search #3) are still relatively scarce: a total of 82 papers, all years considered (search #4). None of these papers is associated with the topic of “citizen science” (search #5).

Search Number	Reference keywords	Number of references	
		Web of Science Accessed 09-09-22	Scopus Accessed 12-09-22
#1	TS= “citizen science”	8,002	7,563 (TITLE-ABS-KEY)
#2	TS= “sustainable urban transformation*”	58	67
#3	TS= “urban sustainability transformation*”	25	21
#4	#2 OR #3	82	87
#5	#1 AND #4	0	0
#6	TS= “urban” AND (“sustainable” OR “sustainability”) AND “transformation*”	3,701	3,968
#7	#1 AND #6	10	6
#8	TS= (“urban” AND (“sustainable” OR “sustainability”)) OR (“urban” AND “transformation*”) OR (“sustainable” OR “sustainability”) AND “transformation*”	98,040	111,648
#9	#1 AND #8	145	128
#10	TS= (“urban” OR “city” OR “cities”) AND (“sustainable” OR “sustainability”) AND (“transformation*” OR “development*”)	48,138	62,026
#11	#1 AND #10	82	73
#12	TS= (((“urban” OR “city” OR “cities”) AND (“sustainable” OR “sustainability”)) OR (“urban” OR “city” OR “cities”) AND (“transformation*” OR “development*”)) OR (“sustainable” OR “sustainability”) AND (“transformation*” OR “development*”))	602,929	722,910
#13	#1 AND #12	645	508
#14	TS= “urban planning”	25,794	73,285
#15	#1 AND #14	60	72
#16	#7 OR #9 OR #11 OR #15	198	194
#17	#16 Web of Science + #16 Scopus, after deduplication	246	

Table 2: Systematic literature search conducted both in Web of Science and Scopus databases.

To be able to fully include all possible interesting papers, the sustainable urban transformation framework was thus enlarged by:

1. Considering in the search the combination of individual words (sustainable or sustainability/ urban / transformation or transformations) in trio (search #6) or pairs (search #8). In combination with “citizen science”, this search produced 10 (search #7) and 145 matches (search #9), respectively.
2. Considering synonyms: “development” for “transformation” and “city” or “cities” for “urban” and repeating the search for the combination of individual words in trio (search #10). The research in pairs with synonyms was discarded for further analysis as it produced a considerable number of matches (602,929 matches, search #12), and remain important even in combination with citizen science (645 matches, search #13).
3. Considering the topic of urban planning, which is another way to approach sustainable urban transformation, as described in section 1.2 (search #14). Associated with citizen science, the search produced a total of 60 more papers (search #15).

Figure 1: Visualization of the different steps necessary to generate the final database. The numbers correspond to the number of references.

All together, these searches produced a total of 198 references with the Web of Science databases and 194 references in Scopus (search #16). After merging the references of the 2 databases and deduplicating them, a total of 246 references was obtained, as illustrated in Fig 1.

These 246 references were complemented by a hand-search done by 5 researchers of 5 institutions⁵, with the goal to include papers that did not appear in the systematic literature search but nevertheless were truly situated at the intersection of “sustainable urban transformation” and “citizen science” frameworks. This hand search produced 82 new references and reduced retrieval bias that always exists in database searches.

After checking for duplicated references, a database of 308 references was critically revised, based on the reading of the full texts, by 3 researchers from 3 different institutions and having different expertise (TU Wien library/information science and bibliometrics; future.lab Research Centre/urban studies and urban planning; UB OpenSystems research group/citizen science). The review of the full texts was carried out independently and separately by each researcher.

The criteria established for the exclusion of the references were the following:

- 1) Only peer-reviewed work was included (articles, conferences proceedings, books' chapter or full books). Presentations or non-published works, such as reports or master thesis, were not included.
- 2) Only references addressing the three components of the search were included: a) citizen science; b) in an urban environment and c) related to sustainable transformation and/or sustainability. When one element was not present, the reference was excluded.

Each researcher established his/her proposed list of references excluded. The references excluded by the 3 researchers were automatically excluded. The other references proposed for exclusion by one or two researchers were discussed case by case.

After exclusion of 34 papers, based on the criteria previously described, a final database containing 277 references was obtained. This final database constitutes the set of references that will be further analyzed.

II.2.2. Evolution of the number of references over time (2012-2021)

The evolution of the number of references has been analyzed over time. The period considered has been the last 10 complete years at the time the literature search was performed: 2012-2021. The absolute number of references for our final database compared with the number of references for “citizen science” are shown in Fig 2.

⁵ TU Wien: TU Wien Bibliothek and future.lab Research Centre; Universitat de Barcelona: OpenSystems research group; Technical University Delft: Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment; TalTech Academy of Architecture and Urban Studies.

Figure 2: Comparison between the evolution of CS papers with aspects related to sustainable urban transformation in Web of Science: (a) Number of references per year for “citizen science”. Search #1 in Table 2; (b) Number of references per year for related to “sustainable urban transformation”. Search #16 in Table 2.

As seen in Fig 2, the magnitude of the numbers of references in each case greatly differs in both cases. In 2021, about 30 times more references addressed “citizen science” than the combination of “citizen science” and “sustainable urban transformation”. Nevertheless, the evolution trend is much quicker for the “sustainable urban transformation” related search: from 2016 to 2021, the number of references has been multiplied by 8. For the same period, the number of “citizen science” references has been only multiplied by 2,6. This trend is further illustrated by Fig 3, where the number of references has been normalized by the sum of all references for the period analyzed, in both cases. It clearly appears that the number of references of the final database experience an exponential growing, where the references associated with “citizen science” only follow a linear evolution.

Figure 3: Number of references per year, normalized by the sum of all years (2012-2021) for the “citizen science” (search #1_blue) and “sustainable urban transformation” (search #16_orange) searches in Web of Science. See Table 2 for more information.

II.2.3 Bibliometric analysis

VOSviewer bibliometric mapping software was applied to create a terms map based on the final set of references selected. A terms map is a two-dimensional map in which terms are placed in such a way that the weighted link between two terms can be interpreted as an indication of the relatedness of the terms. The relatedness of terms is determined based on co-occurrences in publications (title and abstract), which is the frequency with which a term appears alongside other terms. VOSviewer is also automatically generating clusters, where terms are grouped with an optimization method that includes in each cluster highly dense number of links among the terms included in each cluster. Clusters are non-overlapping in VOSviewer so that a term may belong to only one cluster. Each cluster may be seen as a topic. More detailed information can be found in a set of papers describing the algorithm used in VOSviewer (Van Eck & Waltman, 2014; Waltman & Van Eck, 2013). It has been widely demonstrated that terms co-occurrence analysis of a given literature set can effectively represent research hotspots and predicts future areas that may acquire more importance, and thus help researchers to identify topics that have not yet been studied (Krauskopf, 2018; Oladinrin et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2020).

The terms maps are based on the 277 references of the final database. We analyzed the distribution of key terms, present in the title and abstract of the references. To avoid as much as possible biases, all associated keywords with the references were discarded here.

Overview of the results

The 277 references titles and abstracts contain 7701 terms, and the minimum occurrences for the same term was set to 10. 207 terms met the set threshold and once filtered by relevance by VOSviewer, 125 terms were finally selected for the analysis. Out of these terms 125, 2 were merged (urbanisation and urbanization) and 25 were deleted, because they were associated with geographic information (e.g. world, China, etc.) or were too unspecific and thus did not bring relevant information (e.g. article, goal etc.). For a list of the deleted terms, please consult Annex 1.

The 99 remaining terms are visualized in Fig 4. They are associated with 3200 links and a total link strength of 32487. The weight of the node of each term is proportional to the occurrence. All Figures associated with VOSviewer terms map can be consulted in an enlarged version in Annex 2.

The nodes with the same colour belong to a cluster. In the present case, VOSviewer divided the terms into 3 clusters, which have been arbitrarily associated to 3 colours: green (cluster 1), yellow (cluster 2) and purple (cluster 3). The list of terms for each cluster can be found in Table 3. Hereafter, the terms will be written in italics when mentioned in the text.

Figure 4: Overview of the 3 clusters, with all links (3,200) included.

	Cluster 1_Green		Cluster 2_Yellow	Cluster 3_Purple		
	33 terms		16 terms	50 terms		
Terms	Species (109)	<i>Green space (21)</i>	Research (140)	Environment (87)	<i>Source (32)</i>	<i>Student (19)</i>
	Garden (68)	<i>Case study (21)</i>	Impact (89)	Monitoring (66)	<i>Insight (31)</i>	<i>Air quality (18)</i>
	Urban area (63)	<i>Forest (21)</i>	Management (88)	Participation (65)	<i>Place (30)</i>	<i>Volunteer (17)</i>
	Biodiversity (63)	<i>Function (20)</i>	Population (54)	Person (65)	<i>Society (29)</i>	<i>Sustainable city (17)</i>
	Effect (56)	<i>Covid (20)</i>	Understanding (53)	Framework (63)	<i>Sustainable development goal (29)</i>	<i>Topic (16)</i>
	Urbanization (49)	<i>Plant (20)</i>	Need (47)	Nature (61)	<i>Access (28)</i>	<i>Citizen engagement (16)</i>
	Habitat (48)	<i>Wildlife (18)</i>	Gap (43)	Health (57)	<i>Future (26)</i>	<i>Bottom (14)</i>
	Conservation (42)	<i>Insect (16)</i>	Stakeholder (37)	Solution (55)	<i>Smart city (24)</i>	<i>Concentration (14)</i>
	Response (38)	<i>Pollinator (16)</i>	Survey (34)	Participant (54)	<i>Water quality (24)</i>	<i>Urban planner (13)</i>
	Ecosystem service (35)	<i>Fragmentation (15)</i>	Factor (30)	Quality (47)	<i>Air pollution (23)</i>	<i>Older adult (12)</i>
	Observation (35)	<i>Human (15)</i>	Factor (30)	Citizen scientist (46)	<i>Innovation (23)</i>	<i>Prosperity (12)</i>
	Landscape (34)	<i>Presence (15)</i>	Perspective (29)	Initiative (46)	<i>Measurement (23)</i>	<i>Ability (11)</i>
	Site (32)	<i>Urban green space (14)</i>	Collaboration (25)	Water (45)	<i>Public participation (21)</i>	<i>Variety (11)</i>
	Urban environment (30)	<i>Pandemic (13)</i>	Interaction (24)	Resident (37)	<i>Improvement (20)</i>	<i>Physical activity (11)</i>
	Bird (26)	<i>Domestic garden (11)</i>	Decision making (15)	Pollution (35)	<i>Input (20)</i>	<i>Urban sustainability (10)</i>
	Type (26)		Policy maker (11)	Problem (33)		
	Land use (22)			Outcome (33)		
	Tree (22)			Indicator (33)		

Table 3: List of terms for each cluster, as defined by VOSviewer, and ordered by occurrence value, shown into brackets.

Figure 5: Overview of the 3 clusters. Visualization as a function of average year of publication for a term.

1. Concentration (2021,36)
2. Pandemic (2021,23)
3. Covid (2021,20)
4. Citizen engagement (2020,81)
5. Air pollution (2020,61)
6. Green space (2020,57)
7. Sustainable development goal (2020,52)
8. Forest (2020,48)
9. Air quality (2020,23)
10. Health (2020,30)

Table 4: List of the 10 terms with the most recent average publication year, shown into brackets. The terms in green belong to cluster 1 and the ones in purple to cluster 3.

As seen in Fig 4 and Table 3, the number of terms in each cluster differs. The smallest is the yellow one followed by the green and purple ones. In terms of average year of publication, as displayed in Fig 5 and Table 4, the 10 newest items are mainly located inside the purple cluster (*concentration*, *citizen engagement*, *air pollution*, *sustainable development goal*, *air quality* and *health*), although some of the newest items also belong to the green cluster such as *pandemic*, *covid*, *green space* and *forest*.

In terms of density of the terms, each cluster presents different patterns: in the yellow cluster the terms are scattered, in the green one they adopt a more compact structure and finally in the purple cluster, the nodes are very compactly packed. Inside the green cluster, the terms are more strongly related to each other than in the yellow one, which is coherent with a greater internal semantical similarity, as most of the terms in the green cluster are dealing in some way with environmental observation and green spaces. For the purple cluster, the terms are more diverse in terms of meaning but their density is higher, meaning that the overall correlation in-between terms is higher.

are clearly occupying a notable place, compared to the 7 following ones, whose occurrence range from 54 to 30.

As seen in Figs 7 and 8, *impact*, *research* and *management* are very centric nodes, also related with green and purple cluster. This cluster can be typified as an overarching cluster related to the “how” and “why”. As seen in Fig 8, interestingly, the term *policymaker* is connected to the yellow cluster nodes but seldomly to the green cluster and is not connected at all to the purple cluster. This could mean that the policy impact of the purple cluster has not yet been fully potentiated towards the set of references examined.

Figure 7: Impact and research connections. Only links with minimum strength 10 are visualized.

Figure 8: Management and policymaker connections. Only links with minimum strength 10 are visualized.

Purple cluster analysis

Interestingly, if we analyze the 10 most occurrent terms of this cluster (see Table 3), different thematic subgroups can be identified:

- The first one refers to different thematic frames through the terms *environment* (87), *nature* (61) and *health* (57).
- The second one refers to the necessary inclusion of participation in the research: *person* (65), *participation* (65) and *participant* (54).
- The third one finally deals with methodologies and outcomes: *monitoring* (66), *framework* (63), *solution* (55) and *quality* (47).

As commented previously, the purple cluster has more nodes than the other 2. Instead of having clear central ones, as the other 2 clusters, several nodes are of almost equal importance. The two terms with the greatest occurrences are environment (87) and monitoring (61), as seen in Fig 9. Both are clearly linked with the yellow and green cluster but also with most of the terms of the purple one.

Figure 9: Environment and monitoring connections. Only links with minimum strength 10 are visualized.

If we analyze the connections of the anthropogenic terms, such as *participant* or *health* (Fig 10), it clearly appears that these nodes are mostly linked with the yellow cluster nodes, such as *research*, *impact* and *management*, thus confirming the “non-human” centred nature of green cluster. They are also not linked with the *policymaker* term, thus evidencing the lack of relation of policy making with this type of research. The other terms of this cluster include objects of study (e.g. *water* and *air quality*), methodologies and tools (e.g. *monitoring*, *indicator*, *big data*) and actors (*person*, *participant*, *citizen scientist*), thus evidencing that the purple cluster correspond to a complex and diverse ecosystem.

Figure 10: Participant and health connections. Only links with minimum strength 10 are visualized.

OPUSH opportunities and challenges

OPUSH's opportunity is to build a momentum through conceptualizing and testing new research methodologies in a fast growing and in-the-making research environment, thus being possibly able to innovate and to create new avenues in the nexus between CS sustainable urban transformation. The expected OPUSH shift towards open and CS practices, meaning a shift from administrative-technical urban planning to more collaborative actions can easily be visualized taking into account the existing academic ground. Similarly, the shift from expert-oriented urban space optimization towards a collective learning process can also nurture itself from the existing experiences. The planning theory lecture done by Davoudi (2015), emphasizing that everyone is knowledgeable and that the boundaries of knowledge are fluid and overlapping also totally coincides with this interpretation.

Some research fields, likely to be explored in OPUSH, such as those addressing collectives in a vulnerable situation and social and environmental justice do not appear to be widely represented, at first sight. Another challenge spotted by the systematic literature review is the lack of connections between the term "policymakers" and most of the nodes, that might reflect the difficulty to effectively transform the results into political actions.

II.2.4 References in-depth qualitative analysis

Having in mind the bibliometric analysis and the OPUSH opportunities and challenges within the analyzed reference landscape, a further qualitative analysis of the 277 references of the final database was undertaken.

The goal of this analysis was two-fold:

- 1) to further in-depth investigate the **potentials of CS** as a method regarding the challenges of sustainable urban transformation;
- 2) to identify the existing experiences in the field of **social and environmental justice**, especially when collectives in a vulnerable situation are key actors of the research, as it will be the case in OPUSH.

Following a qualitative criterion, the most relevant references for the two goals previously described were selected. The selection of the references was based on the criterium of the first authors of this deliverable which identified a) the references that were bringing the most exhaustive perspectives regarding the potentials of CS and b) the most innovative experiences bridging the topic of social and environmental justice and the participation of collectives in a vulnerable situation.

Potentials of CS for sustainable urban transformation

As previously commented in the systematic literature review, CS and sustainable urban transformation frameworks have a different history and characteristics. Although not many, some authors already analyzed the potentials of CS for sustainable urban transformation and 4 articles with these characteristics have been identified. The main features of these articles analyzed here after are summarized in Table 5.

Title of the papers	Citation	Paper typology	Potentials of CS for sustainable urban transformation
Pathways to urban sustainability: How science can contribute to sustainable development in cities	(Bansard et al., 2019)	Conceptual reflection	<p>Participation in CS projects impact on citizens: 1) enhancing their collaborative skills and their ability to interpret scientific information; 2) enhancing their awareness on urban sustainability, their knowledge of the local environment and can potentially induce a behavioural change.</p> <p>Recommendations: 1) build trust, promote shared ownership and involve diverse stakeholders; 2) enhance collaboration between scientists and cities policymakers.</p> <p>Urban transdisciplinary research can foster capacity building, counter the lack of local level data and produce actionable knowledge related to urban local issues.</p>
Exploring the entry points for citizen science in urban sustainability initiatives	(Colston et al., 2015)	Conceptual reflection	<p>CS is a way to ensure that communities are at the centre of urban development.</p> <p>Transdisciplinary community-led model and “experts-by-experience” should be promoted.</p> <p>Necessary power sharing to have an impact on social and environmental justice.</p>
Citizen Design Science: A strategy for crowd-creative urban design	(Mueller, 2021)	Conceptual Reflection Tool description	<p>Shift from a smart city to a responsive city where citizens are “experts by experience”.</p> <p>ICT solutions to collect a large amount of data.</p> <p>New “Citizen Design Science Discipline” as a merge between CS, Citizen Design and Design Science.</p>
Citizen Science: involving citizens in research projects and urban planning	(Franco & Cappa, 2021)	Conceptual reflection Examples analysis	<p>CS can promote technology-mediated interactions between citizens and public organizations and provide high quantity of data at low cost.</p> <p>Citizens’ involvement is linked to how the issues affect them.</p> <p>CS can provide useful tools to urban planners to solve social and environmental problems.</p>

Table 5: Title, year of publication, authors, typology and main conceptual visions of the selected papers.

In the paper “**Pathways to urban sustainability: How science can contribute to sustainable development in cities**”, Bansard, Hickmann and Kern (2019) explore the pathways of influence for science to foster urban sustainability. Among other possible pathways, they state that urban transdisciplinary research can foster local capacity building. This type of research, including citizen science, can specifically

enhance collaborative skills, ability to interpret scientific information and developed a variety of skills associated with participatory research. They claim that citizen science directly impacts on participating citizens by raising their awareness for sustainability issues, by providing them a better understanding of their local environment and finally by motivating them to undergo behavioural changes. Sharing data collected in the context of field research can also counter the lack of local level data, which is a barrier for developing sustainability policies. They insisted on the need to build trust and shared ownership, as a starting point of participatory research and on the necessity to involve diverse stakeholders in the definition of the research question. These are prerequisites for the generation of actionable knowledge related to urban local issues. Another prerequisite is to enhance collaboration between scientists and city policymakers.

Following a close reasoning, Colston, Vadjunec and Wakeford (2015), in their paper **“Exploring the entry points for citizen science in urban sustainability initiatives”** *“...draw on ideas of social and environmental justice from participatory action research and power relations from political ecology to explore the possibilities for citizen science in urban sustainability initiatives”*. They affirm that *“CS holds potential for ensuring that communities are at the centre of the development of sustainable communities”* and advocates for a truly transdisciplinary community-led model. They exemplify *“how formally trained researchers can co-produce both understanding and plans for action with those whose learning has been experiential”* (also called experts-by-experience). Finally, they conclude that *“those organizing citizen science initiatives should open up spaces in which formally trained researchers give up some of their authority for the cause of accomplishing both sound research and social and environmental justice”*.

In **“Citizen Design Science: A strategy for crowd-creative urban design”**, Mueller (2021) conceptually and practically explore the merging of CS, Citizen Design and Design Science, as illustrated in Fig 11. They advocate for the shift from a smart city to a responsive city, where citizens are experts-by-experience. They also envisage ICT solutions to overcome the lack of representativity of face-to-face workshops, where urban planning solutions are co-designed. After carefully reviewing all three concepts and how they relate to each other, they propose a kit that allows for the citizens to take part in Citizen Design Science projects targeting participatory planning.

Figure 11: The three parts of Citizen Design Science: Citizen Science, Citizen Design and Design Science (Mueller, 2021).

Franco and Cappa (2021) analyzed, from the perspective of participatory urban planning, how CS is emerging as “an effective tool thanks to the development of technologies that favour technology-mediated interactions between citizens and public organizations”. They review the most recent research examples of CS in the urban context, or in other words CS applied to the relationship between cities and citizens. They highlight that the high number of data collected through CS implies a greater impact and thus a smarter city. It also means achieving a greater awareness in the population about relevant topics and strengthening the community. They noted that the participation of citizens to something “they care about”, such as the development of their city or neighborhood is a key point. They also advocate that public administrations should “trust citizens” participating in CS projects because of the high quantity of data, the relevance of the bottom-up approach and the low cost associated. Finally, they conclude that CS is providing useful tools to urban planners to solve social and environmental problems.

Based on these articles’ analysis, Fig 12 is proposing a visualization of the main found components in the form of a “CS pedestrian pathway to Sustainable Urban Transformation”. Four steps are presented illustrating how could be the citizen science potentials for urban sustainable transformation, as envisioned by the articles examined. The actors are two-fold: 1) the citizens communities, as experts-by-experience considering their neighborhoods and 2) the researchers, urban planners and public administrations, willing to implement participation processes.

To set the stage, it is important to consider that the citizen science projects are situated in the field of transdisciplinary research aiming to solve urban social and environmental problems (step 1). The different articles analyzed made evident the necessary values’ framing of the collaborative projects, where capacity building must be considered, while establishing mutual trust and shared ownership (step 2). Another component that repetitively appears is the necessary use of tools, to produce citizen-generated

local data, easily representing high amount of data (step 3). Finally, based on the three previous steps, actionable knowledge for a responsive city can be obtained as an outcome (step 4).

Figure 12: CS pedestrian pathway to Sustainable Urban Transformation. Each step introduces characteristics on how CS and Sustainable Urban Transformation frameworks can interact in the different phases of the research.

Analysis of projects addressing social and environmental justice and collectives in a vulnerable situation

OPUSH project focuses on social and environmental justice as a thematic frame. The final database has been reviewed to focus on the papers addressing these topics. In almost all papers dealing with the intersection of these themes with CS and sustainable urban transformation, social and environmental justice are closely intertwined and cannot be considered separately. Similarly, CS projects targeting social and environmental justice issues always imply collectives in a (more) vulnerable situation. It can also though be noted that most articles consider SDG11 - Make cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable - as a wide framing. Five articles that were specially targeting this thematic frame are hereafter critically reviewed.

Before detailing the most relevant examples, it is important to analyze the discourse that is collectively constructed regarding these issues. The book "Toxic truths, Environmental justice and citizen science in a post-truth age" (Davies & Mah, 2020) gives an overview on how citizen science can address the mostly urban issues linked to environmental justice. In a chapter of the same book, "Science, citizens, and air pollution: constructing environmental (in)justice" (Kenis, 2020) carefully describes and analyzes the discourse construction linked with different citizen science projects on urban air pollution taking place in Antwerp (Belgium) and London (UK). The rationale for action, the choice of the pollutant to measure and the translation of the scientific

facts into specific narratives can be totally different based on the different decisions taken. This is an important analysis to consider, keeping in mind that research is never neutral and that any choice made can impact the research results. The way the research projects are framed thus greatly differs depending on the collectives that have initiated them, the way the data are collected or how the results are transformed into concrete outcomes. This an important starting point to consider, when planning new research projects.

In addition, in all the articles analyzed, the complexity and multifactorial causes of social and environmental issues are considered. The different issues require different tools and methodologies, but the need to carefully analyze the social factors beforehand and to conceptually include the citizens' perception of the issues in the research methodology is a common denominator.

Citation	Title of the papers	Social & Environmental justice issues	Collectives in a vulnerable situation acting as citizen scientists	Outcomes
(Rickenbacher et al., 2019)	Creating environmental consciousness in underserved communities: Implementation and outcomes of community-based environmental justice and air pollution research	Pittsburgh (US) air quality	Low-income and minority communities, more exposed to outdoor and indoor air pollution.	Validation of a community-based model, where underserved communities, a local NGO and academic researchers are involved.
(Newman et al., 2020)	Citizen Science-Informed Community Master Planning: Land Use and Built Environment Changes to Increase Flood Resilience and Decrease Contaminant Exposure	Communities adjacent to concentrated areas of industrial use exposed to elevated levels of pollutants during flood disasters in Manchester, TX (US).	Manchester residents affected by health inequities due to excess exposure.	New participatory master plan for Manchester, achieving a reduction of an average of 41% decrease across all analyzed pollutants.
(Lehnert et al., 2021)	Comparison between mental mapping and land surface temperature in two Czech cities: A new perspective on indication of locations prone to heat stress	Urban Heat Islands (UHI) in two Czech cities	Urban dwellers and visitors and especially the group most vulnerable to heat stress (aged over 60, obese or physically inactive)	Mismatch between "mental" hot spots and temperatures measurements. Need to consider the "overall experience of a place" for urban planning.

(Fell et al., 2021)	Citizen Science in Sweden's Stigmatized Neighborhoods	Unfair and stigmatizing picture of poor places in Swedish deprived neighborhoods	Young males, as "urban outcasts", deprived of social mobility, representation and identity.	New neighborhood narrative and different picture of the neighborhood's social reality
(Soebarto, 2022)	Sustainability for whom? Cities and buildings through the lens of older people	Australian cities are usually planned for the working-age demographic, without considering the perspective of older people	Older people living in Adelaide, Australia.	Case studies on: 1) public and green spaces and 2) indoor thermal comfort. Development of guidelines and strategies relevant to improve the wellbeing of older people, from their perspective.

Table 6: Title, authors, year of publication, issues, collectives and outcomes for the selected papers.

In their article "Creating environmental consciousness in underserved communities: Implementation and outcomes of community-based environmental justice and air pollution research" Rickenbacker, Brown and Bilec (2019) extensively describe the situation related to Pittsburgh (US) air quality. In their analysis, they explain that vulnerable (low-income and minority) communities are more exposed to outdoor and indoor air pollution. They propose a community-based model, based on the collaboration of academic researchers with a local non-profit and community-based organization and the underserved communities. They described strategies that have successfully addressed gaps regarding recruitment and retention, based on training, workshops and collective measurements campaign. Finally, they conclude that "*in order for long-term societal goals to be met, there must be multiple spheres of influence and a shared vision from communities and researchers alike. Goals that are developed and executed from a community's definition of needs, ensures participation from project inception through to evaluation.*"

Another form of contamination is the one provoked by flooding, for neighborhoods that are close to concentrated areas of industrial land use, as evidenced in the paper by Newman *et al.* (2020). In the case of Manchester, TX (US), those neighborhoods are also associated with socially vulnerable populations, affected by floodings associated with hurricanes extreme rain falls. The authors demonstrate how interdisciplinary research combining public health, landscape architecture, urban planning with local-scale CS can contribute to solve issues to contamination and flooding.

In the last 5 years, another topic linked to environmental justice has arouse a growing interest: the phenomenon of extreme heat or Urban Heat Islands (UHI) in cities. The vast majority of the articles mostly deal with the measurements of the urban temperatures but Lehnert *et al.* (2021) bring to the forefront an additional dimension: the subjectively-perceived thermal (dis)comfort. They interestingly argue that non only

the objective urban temperature but also the “*thermal (dis)comfort of urban dwellers and visitors... strongly influences habitability, attractiveness and the perceived quality of the area, determining the quality of life in cities and influencing social and cultural life-styles*” and therefore should be taken into account for urban planning. Using participatory mapping techniques and involving large groups of citizens in two cities, they compare “mental” hot spots and temperatures measurements. They claim that in half of the cases, the greatest reported thermal discomfort is not matching with the hottest observed temperatures, thus emphasizing the need to take into the “overall experience of a place”.

The importance of the “sense of place” is also central in the article “Citizen Science in Sweden’s Stigmatized Neighborhoods” written by Fell *et al.* (2021). In this paper, they investigate territorial stigmatization in three Swedish deprived neighborhoods, based on the contributions of young males, that act as citizen scientist and shared their vision “from inside”. Using the App “Our Voice”⁶, developed by the Stanford Faculty of Medicine, they reported new neighborhood narratives and social realities, that contrast with the unfair and stigmatizing picture of poor places disseminated by the media, police and politicians. The App is largely based on the photovoice methodology.

Another collective that is in a more vulnerable situation in cities is the one of older people. As evidenced by Soebarto (2022) “...*cities, particularly our inner-city built environments, are spaces that are usually imagined, planned and structured for a younger, working-age demographic*” and “...*despite the fact that older share a significant proportion of our population, older people are still not the focus on mainstream thinking, planning and designing our cities up to the present time.*” Through two case studies, Soebarto demonstrates that older people, acting as citizen scientists, can bring new perspectives to “*achieve cities that are truly sustainable, environmentally and socially*”.

The previous articles were deliberately chosen as they are associated with cities somehow comparable with the ones where OPUSH research will take place: Vienna, Barcelona, Delft and Tallin. Nevertheless, SDG11 is also highly (or even more) relevant for cities of the Global South. Croese, Dominique and Raimundo (2021) for example, used CS for co-producing urban knowledge in various cities of Angola and Mozambique. Hachmann, Jokar Arsanjani and Vaz (2018) explored the fields of Volunteered Geographic Information and Citizen Science to gather information about informal settlements, following a bottom-up approach. Wolff *et al.* (2021) used CS to investigate the flood monitoring in urban informal settlements in Fiji and Indonesia. Finally, Water justice in Cape Town’s low-income neighborhoods was addressed by Enqvist *et al.* (2022).

⁶ Our Voice: Citizen Science for Health Equity. <https://med.stanford.edu/ourvoice.html>

Figure 13: Categorization of issues, collectives, transformation and methodologies and tools for the selected case studies addressing CS and sustainable urban transformation.

Finally, the different themes of the case studies analyzed are categorized in Fig 13. Of course, this figure does not pretend to give a complete overview of the diversity of existing projects but at least allow to explore the most common strategies. In all categories, the different subcategories are not exclusive and some projects include more than one subcategory.

The social and environmental justice issues considered range from issues linked with external environmental factors such as extreme heat, air pollution or flooding. These factors are anthropogenic (air pollution) and/or related to climate change (extreme heat/flooding). Other issues are more directly linked with social exclusion like the stigmatization of given places or “invisible collectives” that are not (or less) considered when planning cities, such as older people for examples.

As for the collectives in a vulnerable situation involved in CS projects, low income and stigmatized communities are often cited. In most of the cases, they are also exposed to greater environmental hazards. Collectives that are also more vulnerable to environmental health issues are also involved in some cases, such for example the case of obese people more vulnerable to heat waves.

The transformations produced in the studies are diverse. They range from the validation of complex bottom-up methodologies to the proposal of new participative urban planning strategies and new policy guidelines. In almost all cases, policymakers are being informed of the results at the end of the project but are seldomly involved during the whole research cycle.

The methodologies and tools used are extremely diverse and so are the disciplines associated. Some studies used some Volunteered Geographic Information methodologies and collective mapping. Other are grounded in traditional social sciences methodologies like photovoice. The involvement of the communities is sometimes very intense and can include collective measurements, data interpretation and even peer training. Some projects create their own digital tools whereas other are based on tuneable Apps like the “Our Voice” App that was used for several community-based projects.

III. Conclusions

This Deliverable explores the intersection of CS and sustainable urban transformation frameworks. After defining these frameworks, a systematic literature review is being conducted. The results show that the number of associated articles is exponentially growing. The concepts associated with the articles can be classified into three clusters that are critically discussed.

The OPUSH scope is discussed in relation to the three clusters and is associated with an intersectional space is still “in the making” and highly diverse.

An in-depth qualitative analysis of the articles allowed to start proposing potentials of CS for sustainable urban transformation, based on four steps. An exploration of the different examples of projects based on social and environmental justice issues and involving collectives in a vulnerable situation reveals a variety of issues, collectives and outcomes, that are related one to the other in a complex way. The methodologies and tools used are also very diverse and associated with disciplines such as geography or social sciences.

OPUSH thus situates itself in a very fluid environment, that is changing rapidly, where no consolidated conceptual frame has been established, but a myriad of opportunities is flourishing. The challenge and value of OPUSH can thus consist of working on a new consolidated conceptual frame for this intersection and demonstrating its viability through different case studies. An additional challenge to be tackled is the need for more connection with policymakers and the transformation of the scientific results into concrete actions.

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Annex 1. VoSViewer parameters

- "Urbanisation" and "Urbanization" have been merged inside the Ris source file.
- VoSViewer analysis has been done based on the title and abstract of the references.
- Abstracts labels and copyright have been ignored.
- The full counting option has been activated.
- Minimum occurrence was set to 10: 207 terms among the 7701 encountered were selected.
- The relevance filter reduced the number of terms from 207 to 124.
- 25 terms were deleted based on these criteria: acronyms, geographic indication and unspecify terms were deleted.

Geocraft	Sustainable development	Way
Sdg	World	Review
Wdna	China	Focus
Sdgs	Australia	Science
Nbs	Paper	Order
Occurrence	Term	Relationship
Article	Citizen science data	Relation
Goal	Concept	Area
Citizen science project		

Annex 2. Enlarged VoSViewer figures

Enlarged Figure 4: Overview of the 3 clusters, with all links (3,200) included.

Figure 10: Participant and health connections. Only links with minimum strength 10 are visualized.

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